

BRIDGING POLICY GAPS THROUGH ISO 59000 STANDARDS IN EUROPEAN WASTE MANAGEMENT TRANSITIONS

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Abstract: *The European Union faces significant challenges in meeting its 2025-2035 circular economy targets, with 18 member states at risk of missing municipal waste recycling goals. This paper examines how the newly published ISO 59000 standards family (ISO 59004, ISO 59010, and ISO 59020) addresses these implementation gaps. By analyzing the standards' requirements and obligations, this paper examines the potential to harmonize measurement methodologies, facilitate value network transitions, and establish transparent circularity performance indicators across diverse organizational contexts. The findings show that the standards focus on systems thinking, resource traceability, and core indicators, and that they provide practical solutions to the current deficiencies in European waste management. The paper contributes to closing the gap between theory and practice in circular economy implementation by mapping specific standard provisions to EU policy challenges and identifying potential implementation barriers that require policy attention and organizational capacity-building.*

Keywords: Circular Economy, ISO 59000 Family of Standards, Waste Management, EU Policy Implementation, Circularity Indicators, Implementation Barriers.

1. INTRODUCTION

The European Union has positioned itself as a global leader in circular economy policy through its Circular Economy Action Plans (CEAP) [1] of 2015 and 2020, establishing ambitious targets for waste reduction and resource circularity. However, implementation challenges persist across member states, with significant gaps between policy ambitions and operational realities.

Recent assessments reveal critical deficiencies in EU waste management systems. Eighteen member states are at risk of missing the 2025 municipal waste recycling target of 55% [2]. While the EU has achieved progress in recycling rates, from 37.2% in 2013 to 48.0% in 2023, and reduced municipal waste generation from 534 kg per capita in 2021 to 511 kg in 2023, significant volumes remain diverted to non-circular pathways, with 25.2% incinerated and 22.5% landfilled, representing persistent barriers to achieving full circularity [3]. Recent assessments show significant variation in the performance of the circular economy among Member States. While some European countries, such as Germany, Austria, and Slovenia, have achieved municipal waste recycling rates exceeding 60% according to Eurostat data from 2022, several southern and eastern European countries, in stark contrast, recorded recycling rates below 20%, like Greece and Cyprus, with Romania and Malta at critically low levels of 12% [4]. This implementation gap can be attributed to several factors. Some of them can be differences in infrastructure investment, inconsistencies in waste measurement, and reporting methodologies, including unclear definitions of "recycling" and "recovery," as well as

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variations in value chain management [5]. As of 2023, Europe's circularity rate is about 12%, and the goal is to double it to 24% by 2030 [6]. Against this backdrop, the International Organization for Standardization published the ISO 59000 standards family in May 2024, providing the first globally harmonized framework for circular economy implementation and measurement. The family consists of three interconnected standards: ISO 59004 (vocabulary, principles, and implementation guidance) [7], ISO 59010 (business model and value network transition) [8], and ISO 59020 (measuring and assessing circularity performance) [9]. This paper addresses the research question: "How can the ISO 59000 standards' requirements and obligations address current implementation gaps in European waste management?" by analyzing the three standards, aiming to extract core requirements, map these provisions to identified EU policy implementation challenges, and identify potential barriers.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a document-based qualitative comparative analysis to examine how the ISO 59000 standards family addresses implementation gaps in EU circular economy and waste management policies. The research follows a three-phase analytical protocol: (1) structured extraction of requirements from standards documentation, (2) thematic mapping of these requirements to identified EU policy challenges, and (3) systematic identification of implementation barriers through cross-referencing with empirical literature.

Primary data comprise three ISO standards published in May 2024: ISO 59004:2024 (Circular economy – Vocabulary, principles and guidance for implementation), ISO 59010:2024 (Circular economy – Guidance on the transition of business models and value networks), and ISO 59020:2024 (Circular economy—Measuring and assessing circularity performance) [7,8,9]. Secondary data include: (i) official European Commission circularity monitoring reports and waste management assessments (2020-2025); (ii) Eurostat municipal waste statistics and circular economy indicators; and (iii) European Environment Agency early warning assessments on recycling target compliance.

3. THE ISO 59000 STANDARDS FRAMEWORK AND EU WASTE MANAGEMENT ALIGNMENT

The ISO 59000 family establishes six interconnected circular economy principles: systems thinking, value creation, value sharing, resource stewardship, resource traceability, and ecosystem resilience. These principles mandate that organizations adopt life-cycle perspectives when considering impacts on environmental, social, and economic systems, moving beyond narrow organizational boundaries to embrace systemic approaches.

ISO 59004 defines the circular economy as "an economic system that uses a systemic approach to maintain a circular flow of resources, by recovering, retaining or adding to their value, while contributing to sustainable development." The standard establishes mandatory requirements for design for circularity, circular procurement, and systematic resource management hierarchies (refuse, rethink, reduce, reuse, repair, refurbish, remanufacture, repurpose, recycle and recover).

ISO 59010 provides business-oriented guidance for transitioning value creation models and value networks from linear to circular configurations. It addresses the practical challenge that circular economy implementation typically demands the restructuring of organizational value-creation models and inter-organizational value networks through structured governance frameworks and shared infrastructure development.

ISO 59020 specifies requirements for measuring and assessing circularity performance through mandatory core circularity indicators and comprehensive measurement frameworks. It establishes that resource inflows and outflows must be quantified with 100% mass balance, creating standardized measurement approaches applicable at regional, inter-organizational, organizational, and product system levels.

3.1 Policy Alignment and Implementation Challenges

The systematic mapping of the ISO 59000 family of standards (ISO 59004, ISO 59010, ISO 59020) to EU circular economy and waste management policy objectives unveils both significant opportunities and a spectrum of implementation challenges that warrant nuanced consideration.

The key challenges identified span technical, organizational, economic, and governance domains:

- **Technical barriers** are prevalent, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and municipal waste systems, which frequently lack advanced digital infrastructure for comprehensive material flow tracking and data collection, as mandated by ISO 59020 core indicators. Limitations in the compatibility of existing national statistical methodologies also present obstacles to harmonized measurement and reporting [10].
- **Organizational challenges** center on resistance to shifts in established business models, insufficient cross-functional coordination, and inadequate capacity for systems thinking. The transition toward circular value-creation frameworks, as advocated by ISO 59010, requires disrupting conventional revenue models and developing significant capabilities across the enterprise.
- **Economic and market barriers** include persistent uncertainty about the quality and availability of secondary raw materials, as well as challenges with capital coordination for updating infrastructure and adopting circular procurement approaches. Market structures often favor inexpensive virgin materials over recycled inputs, interfering with circular adoption.
- **Governance and coordination complexities** arise from divergent stakeholder interests within multi-stakeholder value networks, trust deficits stemming from prior collaboration failures, and cross-jurisdictional regulatory inconsistencies that complicate the development of shared infrastructure and coordinated investment strategies.

Figure 1 presents the potentials of connecting individual standard provisions to specific EU targets and illuminating areas of synergy as well as potential obstacles to effective adoption. ISO 59004 introduces circularity requirements for products and procurement to address packaging and secondary materials goals, ISO 59010 enables coordinated action on EPR (Extended Producer Responsibility) and bio-waste processing through value network provisions. At the same time, ISO 59020 ensures rigorous target tracking and comparability with mandatory indicators and harmonized measurement. Key interventions for overcoming implementation challenges include:

Technical capacity building through investment in digital infrastructure, comprehensive staff training, and the establishment of technical assistance programs for SMEs and public sector actors. Shared infrastructure initiatives supported by targeted policy can help distribute costs and operational burdens. An approach could be to establish EU-funded pilot programs to deploy digital product passports in member states, targeting SMEs in the packaging and electronics sectors.

Economic incentive alignment through demonstration projects, risk-sharing mechanisms, and policy interventions to address market failures and build confidence in the quality of secondary materials.

Figure 1. ISO 59000 standards implementation framework for EU waste management targets, Source: authors

Organizational change management employing change management programs, leadership-driven initiatives, and gradual transitions designed to minimize disruption while building strategic competencies.

Governance structure development implementing transparent benefit-sharing, robust dispute resolution, and participatory governance mechanisms to balance collective interests and foster trust in collaborative networks.

The identified intervention mechanisms are summarized in Table 1, highlighting their alignment with the requirements for implementing the ISO 59000 family of standards and the expected performance improvements to enhance circularity.

Table 1. Key intervention mechanisms supporting ISO 59000 uptake in EU waste systems

Source: authors

INTERVENTION AREA	PRACTICAL MEASURES	SUPPORTED ISO REQUIREMENTS	EXPECTED OUTCOMES
Technical capacity	Digital product passports, SME support, training programs [10,11]	ISO 59020	Improved traceability & indicator compliance [9]
Market development	Green procurement, quality certification, risk-sharing [12]	ISO 59004	Higher secondary material demand [7]
Organizational change	Leadership programs, phased transition planning [8]	ISO 59010	Adoption of circular value models [8, 13]
Infrastructure & governance	Shared facilities, cooperation platforms [10]	ISO 59010 + 59020	Coordinated cross-sector implementation [14]

The ISO 59000 standards provide foundational tools for reinforcing EU policy frameworks:

- **Waste Framework Directive Enhancement:** ISO 59020 guidelines for circularity measurement provide harmonized methodologies for member states to demonstrate compliance with recycling targets, supporting consistent reporting while preserving flexibility in national strategies.
- **Circular Economy Act Provisions:** Forthcoming EU legislation can leverage ISO 59000 requirements to define standardized quality benchmarks for secondary raw materials, enhancing market functionality through harmonization and transparency.
- **Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) Optimization:** Governance frameworks in ISO 59010 can inform EPR scheme design, ensuring effective multi-stakeholder coordination and enabling robust measurement of circular economy outcomes.

EU-funded capacity-building initiatives are critical to the circular economy transition, as they enable organizations to modernize their digital infrastructure, improve data management, and build organizational expertise in circular principles. Together with green public procurement and certification, these programs stimulate demand for secondary raw materials and reduce financial and market barriers, especially for SMEs and public authorities [15,16,17].

Additionally, targeted infrastructure investment, coordinated through EU cohesion policy, streamlines resources pooling and helps harmonize regulatory frameworks, thereby lowering adoption barriers. Key success factors for ISO 59000 implementation include advanced digital tracking systems, multidisciplinary capacity-building, and transparent inter-organizational collaboration, creating an enabling environment for accelerated circular economy adoption across the EU [16,17]. Positive examples already exist, though few in number. The Netherlands demonstrated positive progress in 2024 by implementing ISO 59020 core indicators across its packaging value network [14], achieving a 15% improvement in traceability within six months. Success factors included mandatory digital product passports, €5 million in grants for SMEs, and a governance structure with over 40 organizations. Similarly, Germany's National Circular Economy Strategy (adopted December 2024) emphasizes standardization aligned with ISO 59000 principles. This document prioritizes digital product passports and supports high-quality recycling standards for plastics and electrical equipment. It also includes cross-sectoral traceability systems, demonstrating how national policies can implement international circularity frameworks [18].

4. CONCLUSION

The ISO 59000 standards family provides comprehensive frameworks to address gaps in European waste management implementation, offering practical solutions to challenges that prevent achieving the 2025-2035 circular economy targets. The analysis demonstrates precise alignment between standard provisions and EU policy objectives, while identifying specific implementation challenges that require targeted attention. The standards' integrated approach, combining principle-based implementation guidance (ISO 59004), value network transition frameworks (ISO 59010), and mandatory measurement requirements (ISO 59020), addresses the systemic nature of circular economy transitions. However, successful adoption requires careful attention to implementation challenges spanning technical capacity, economic incentives, organizational change, and governance coordination. Critical success factors include phased adoption approaches that build capacity incrementally, policy support addressing market failures and coordination challenges, and recognition that circular economy transitions require simultaneous attention to technical, organizational, and inter-organizational dimensions. For the EU's path toward its 2050 climate-neutrality and circular-economy vision, the ISO 59000 standards provide practical tools for accelerating progress, while the implementation challenge analysis guides policymakers in designing support mechanisms to address identified barriers. Future research priorities should include longitudinal studies, cross-country comparisons, and cost-benefit analyses of ISO 59000 adoption to inform effective policy design and organizational strategies.

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